

Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Barplot showing summary of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) per species grouped by different categories. Left panel shows upregulated DEGs per species. Right panel shows downregulated DEGs per species.

Figure S2. Barplot showing total number of cuticle protein families in *L. vannamei* detected per cluster

Figure S3. GO enrichment plots showing significantly enriched terms per gene expression cluster in *L. vannamei*

Figure S4. Moulting gene expression clusters in *D. melanogaster*

Figure above shows the gene expression clusters of *D. melanogaster* samples and their corresponding phylostratum composition.

(cont.)

Figure S5. GO enrichment plots showing significantly enriched terms per gene expression cluster in *D. melanogaster*